

Effects of Reactivity Insertion Patterns on Waiting Time Distributions in Weak Source Reactor Startup

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ABSTRACT

Reactivity insertion patterns influence the evolution of stochastic neutron kinetics during weak source startup in the absence of external neutron sources. Time dependent Monte Carlo simulations were performed using the Reactor Monte Carlo code developed at Tsinghua University. Two representative insertion schemes, stepwise insertion and linear insertion, were examined under different initial subcritical conditions. For each case, 100 independent realizations were carried out using a simplified cylindrical reactor model. Results indicate that for stepwise insertion, larger inserted reactivity leads to longer stabilization times, whereas deeper subcritical states accelerate stabilization. For linear insertion, the waiting time becomes highly sensitive to the insertion rate as the system approaches criticality. These findings provide quantitative insights into the relationship between reactivity insertion mode and subcritical waiting time, contributing to the optimization of weak source startup schemes.

Keywords: Monte Carlo; weak source startup; stochastic kinetics; reactivity insertion

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear energy plays a crucial role in achieving global carbon neutrality and ensuring energy security [1-3]. As advanced reactor designs prioritize safety, efficiency, and economy, innovative startup methods are being developed to reduce reliance on external neutron sources. Weak source startup, which relies solely on spontaneous fission neutrons to initiate the chain reaction, eliminates the need for costly and radioactive sources such as Cf-252 or Sb-Be.[4].

However, in the absence of an external neutron source, the reactor core experiences an extremely weak neutron field at the beginning of startup. This weak field introduces pronounced stochastic behavior in neutron population evolution, especially in subcritical conditions, where neutron chains are short and do not overlap significantly [6,7]. Traditional deterministic neutron

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kinetics models are inadequate to describe this early stage, necessitating the use of stochastic neutron kinetics and Monte Carlo simulation methods [8-10].

During the startup process, as reactivity is gradually introduced, the system transitions from stochastic to deterministic behavior. The timing and manner of reactivity insertion play decisive roles in determining the transition time, neutron population growth rate, and operational safety margins [2,11]. Improper reactivity introduction may delay the transition, extend the subcritical waiting period, or even risk premature supercritical behavior.

Previous research has primarily focused on the influence of source strength and simple geometry on stochastic neutron kinetics [2,12]. Nevertheless, the reactivity insertion pattern—specifically, whether reactivity is added instantaneously (stepwise) or continuously (linearly) has not been comprehensively examined. The reactivity insertion pattern affects both the transient response of neutron population and the distribution of subcritical waiting times [13].

This study therefore aims to systematically analyze the effects of reactivity insertion patterns on weak source startup. Using the Reactor Monte Carlo (RMC) code developed by Tsinghua University's REAL team [14], a time-dependent stochastic simulation was performed under various subcritical conditions.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology integrates a Monte Carlo-based stochastic kinetics framework enhanced by customized implementations that allow dynamic reactivity control, fission multiplicity modeling, and multi-sample statistical analysis.

2.1. Reactor Model and Physical Parameters

A simplified cylindrical reactor model was constructed to represent the essential behavior of weak source startup. As shown in Figure 1. The active core has a radius of 50 cm and a height of 140 cm, consisting of homogenized UO_2 fuel with 3.1% enrichment and water moderator. The surrounding reflector comprises 30 cm of water radially and 20 cm axially. A B_4C control rod is centrally located to manipulate reactivity. The effective multiplication factors (k_{eff}) were obtained through static RMC calculations. The spontaneous fission source strength of the core was approximately 4.1×10^4 n/s, based on the isotopic composition and fission probabilities of U-235 and U-238.

Figure 1. Cross-sectional diagram of the test case.

2.2. Fission Multiplicity and Source Modeling

To more accurately reproduce stochastic behavior in the weak neutron field, the number of secondary neutrons produced in each fission event was treated as a random variable following a Gaussian fission multiplicity distribution, rather than using the traditional deterministic mean fission yield. The probability that exactly n neutrons are emitted in a single fission event is expressed as:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\nu} P_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{(\nu - \bar{\nu} + 1/2 + b)/\sigma_e} e^{-t^2/2} dt \quad (1)$$

The neutron source term was configured as a spontaneous fission source without any external neutron injection. The source strength and spatial distribution were computed from the total mass of fissile isotopes, their spontaneous fission rates, and material density. These parameters were integrated into the RMC input configuration to initiate startup simulations.

2.3. Multi-Sample Statistical Simulation

Weak neutron fields exhibit significant fluctuations, meaning a single Monte Carlo realization may not accurately represent ensemble behavior. Therefore, a multi-sample simulation framework was adopted. Independent simulations were executed by altering the random number seed in each run, effectively generating a set of statistically uncorrelated histories. The ensemble of results allows estimation of the probability density and cumulative distributions of neutron population, fission rate, and flux.

2.4. Reactivity Insertion Schemes

To comprehensively evaluate transient behavior under different reactivity insertion strategies, two canonical reactivity insertion schemes were analyzed: stepwise insertion and linear insertion.

(a) Stepwise Reactivity Insertion:

Reactivity was introduced instantaneously to simulate abrupt control rod movements or rapid concentration changes in soluble absorbers. Inserted reactivities of 60, 120, and 260 pcm were applied.

(b) Linear Reactivity Insertion:

This mode represents continuous reactivity increase through gradual control rod withdrawal or boron dilution. Linear ramp rates of 1, 16, and 54 pcm/s were used, corresponding to slow, moderate, and fast insertion speeds.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Stepwise Reactivity Insertion

To study the effect of stepwise reactivity insertion on the subcritical waiting time, initial control rod positions were chosen as -40 cm ($k_{eff} = 0.977130$), -30 cm ($k_{eff} = 0.989709$), and -26 cm ($k_{eff} = 0.995300$). Reactivity was introduced in steps of 60, 120, and 260 pcm. A total of 100 samples were simulated, with 300 s of computation at the initial subcritical state, followed by another 300 s after the stepwise reactivity insertion. The waiting time distribution is shown in the figure below. Due to space limitations, only three images are shown, with the others having similar shapes.

Figure 2. Subcritical waiting time distribution after stepwise reactivity insertion of 60 pcm (initial control rod position at -40 cm)

Figure 3. Subcritical waiting time distribution after stepwise reactivity insertion of 120 pcm (initial control rod position at -40 cm)

Figure 4. Subcritical waiting time distribution after stepwise reactivity insertion of 260 pcm (initial control rod position at -40 cm)

To examine the relationship between waiting time, initial subcriticality, and reactivity insertion magnitude, we statistically analyzed the times at which each distribution reached 90% cumulative probability, as shown in the table below. The results indicate that for the same reactivity insertion, deeper subcriticality leads to a quicker transition to subcritical stability. Conversely, for the same initial subcriticality, a larger reactivity insertion results in a slower transition, requiring a longer waiting time. This is consistent with the behavior of neutron population in the subcritical steady state: the larger the effective multiplication factor k_{off} , the higher the stabilized neutron population, and the longer the time required to reach that state.

Table I. Comparison of different initial subcriticality and stepwise reactivity insertion magnitudes.

Initial Rod Position (cm)	Inserted Reactivity (pcm)	Subcritical Waiting Time to 90% Probability (s)
-40	260	75
-30	260	125
-26	260	250
-40	120	61
-30	120	112
-26	120	150
-40	60	40
-30	60	75
-26	60	120

3.2. Linear Reactivity Insertion

To study the effect of linear reactivity insertion rates on the subcritical waiting time, the initial control rod positions were selected as -40 cm ($k_{\text{eff}} = 0.977130$), -30 cm ($k_{\text{eff}} = 0.989709$),

and -26 cm ($k_{eff} = 0.995300$). A total reactivity of 60 pcm was introduced, with linear insertion rates of 1 , 16 , and 54 pcm/s. A total of 100 samples were simulated, and the waiting time distribution is shown in the figure below. Due to space limitations, only three images are shown, with the others having similar shapes.

Figure 5. Subcritical Waiting Time Distribution for Linear Reactivity Insertion Rate of 1 pcm/s (Initial Control Rod Position at -40 cm)

Figure 6. Subcritical Waiting Time Distribution for Linear Reactivity Insertion Rate of 16 pcm/s (Initial Control Rod Position at -40 cm)

Figure 7. Subcritical Waiting Time Distribution for Linear Reactivity Insertion Rate of 54 pcm/s (Initial Control Rod Position at -40 cm)

To investigate the relationship between waiting time, initial subcriticality, and linear reactivity insertion rate, we performed a statistical analysis of the times at which each distribution

reached 90% cumulative probability, as shown below (the starting point for waiting time is the moment after the final 60 pcm reactivity is introduced). It can be observed that for a constant reactivity insertion rate, deeper initial subcriticality leads to a faster transition to subcritical stability. When the initial subcriticality is deeper, the reactivity insertion rate has little effect on the time to reach subcritical stability. However, as the initial subcriticality approaches criticality, the transition time to subcritical stability changes significantly with varying insertion rates. This is consistent with the behavior of the neutron population in the subcritical steady state: as keff approaches unity, the stabilized neutron population diverges toward infinity, and the time required to reach that state also tends to infinity, leading to inherent instability.

Table II. Comparison of Different Initial Subcriticality and Reactivity Insertion Rates

Initial Rod Position (cm)	Reactivity Insertion Rate (pcm/s)	Subcritical Waiting Time to 90% Probability (s)
-40	1	60
-30	1	75
-26	1	100
-40	16	60
-30	16	75
-26	16	160
-40	54	55
-30	54	70
-26	54	105

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study examined how different reactivity insertion patterns influence the waiting time during weak source startup under subcritical conditions. The results show that the waiting time is governed jointly by the initial subcriticality and the temporal form of reactivity introduction.

For stepwise insertion, larger reactivity additions prolong the waiting time, particularly when the system is close to criticality. In contrast, deeper initial subcritical states shorten the waiting period. This behavior is consistent with the dependence of the stabilized neutron population on the effective multiplication factor.

For linear insertion, the insertion rate has little influence when the system remains well below criticality. As the effective multiplication factor approaches unity, however, the waiting time becomes increasingly sensitive to the rate of reactivity increase.

Overall, the waiting time during weak source startup reflects the evolution of neutron multiplication under time dependent reactivity conditions. The results provide a quantitative reference for selecting appropriate reactivity control strategies during startup operations.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Huang, W. “Challenges and Countermeasures for High-Quality Nuclear Energy Development under Carbon Neutral Goals.” China Engineering Consulting, (2021).
- [2] Jia, C., Wang, W., and Wang, K. “Simulation of Reactor Startup Without External Neutron Source Based on RMC.” Proceedings of RPHA 2023, Gyeongju, Korea (2023).
- [3] Zhang, W., Fang, X. “Analysis of Passive Startup of 320 MW PWR Without External Neutron Source.” Applied Technology, (2014).
- [4] Chen, X., Ye, B. “Passive Loading and Startup in PWR Nuclear Power Plants.” Science and Technology Innovation and Application, (2015).
- [5] Shang, X., and Wang, K. “Burst Waiting Time Simulation of Caliban Pulse Reactor with RMC.” Transactions of the American Nuclear Society, 117(1), 686-689 (2017).
- [6] Qiu, Y., Liang, J., Wang, K., et al. “New Strategies of Sensitivity Analysis in Continuous-Energy Monte Carlo Code RMC.” Annals of Nuclear Energy, 81, 50-61 (2015).
- [7] She, D., Liu, Y., and Wang, K. “Development of Burnup Methods and Capabilities in Monte Carlo Code RMC.” Annals of Nuclear Energy, 51, 289-294 (2013).
- [8] Guo, J., Liu, S., Shang, X., et al. “Coupled Neutronics/Thermal-Hydraulics Analysis of a Full PWR Core Using RMC and CTF.” Annals of Nuclear Energy, 109, 327-336 (2017).
- [9] Liu, S., Yuan, Y., Yu, J., et al. “On-the-Fly Temperature-Dependent Cross-Section Treatment in RMC Code.” Annals of Nuclear Energy, 94, 144-149 (2016).
- [10] Jia, C., Wang, K. “Analysis of Factors Affecting Stochastic Neutron Kinetics in Weak Source Startup Based on RMC.” Postdoctoral Research Report, Tsinghua University (2024).
- [11] Wang, G., and Yu, G. “Calculating Control Rod Differential Worth Using Adjoint-Weighted Method.” Transactions of the American Nuclear Society, 116, (2017).
- [12] She, D., Wang, K., Yu, G. “Asymptotic Wielandt and Superhistory Methods for Source Convergence in Monte Carlo Criticality Calculation.” Nuclear Science and Engineering, 172(2), 127-137 (2012).
- [13] Wang, K., Liu, S., Li, Z., et al. “Analysis of BEAVRS Two-Cycle Benchmark Using RMC Based on Full Core Detailed Model.” Progress in Nuclear Energy, 98, 301-312 (2017).